
Impact of Agricultural Development on Water Degradation in Walwa Tahsil

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Abstract:

Water is the most important substance on the earth plant. The survival of all plants and animals depends upon the water if there was no water there would be no life on Earth. Cooking meals washing clothes and cleaning household utensils such as billies saucepans, crockery, and cutlery are household usages of water related to the kitchen bathing keeping houses and communities clean, recreation; such as swimming pools keeping plants alive in gardens and parks, Water is also essential for the healthy growth of farm crops and farm stock and is used to manufacture many products. As per the basic needs of humans, people need water to drink which must be hygienic. This means that the water must be free from germs and chemicals and be pure unhygienic. (Not cloudy). Water that is safe for drinking is called **potable water**. Disease-causing germs and chemicals are found in drinking water supplies. When this happens, the water becomes polluted or contaminated and when people drink it or come in contact it attacks the immune system of the human body. Most of diseases are spread from the water. Water that is not safe to drink is said to be non-potable. Throughout history, there have been many occasions when hundreds of thousands of people have died because disease-causing germs have been spread through a by a polluted water supply. It happens less frequently now, one of the reasons behind this is, that people in many countries, prefer to be sure about drinking water supplies and it must be portable. Water supplies are routinely checked if such sources are not safe all the action taken to make sure that drinking water is potable is called **water treatment**.

Sangli district is known as a developed district. There are 10 tahsil and 728 villages in this district. Because of its geology, the district comes in tahsil in the western part of it i.e. Shirala walwa, Palus, Miraj talukas use of water resources situated positive; but the effect of this agricultural development has been degradation, so the present topic concerns the impact of agricultural development on the environment. According to the Census of India (2011), 69 % of the population is engaged in agriculture. India is a country with (2001) 70% population living in villages and having agriculture as the major earning source. Lots of the farmers are reeling from poverty since ages. The successive government has cared to increase productivity. The new techniques thus invented and should be introduced for the poor farming community in our country to enhance production and also bring down the skyrocketing prices of agricultural products. But here is a problem occurs; that is the impact of Agricultural development on Water, degradation.

Keywords: *Water the Destruction of Ecosystems; Habitat Destruction; Pollution, Crop Rotation, Water Use, Water Logging, Irrigation, and Water Pollution.*

Introduction:

‘Agriculture’ in Agricultural Geography implies the subject matter, and ‘geography’ gives the way of viewing or investigating the subject matter. Etymologically, Agricultural geography deals with “*The science or art of cultivating*

soil, growing and harvesting of crops, domestication of animals and raising of livestock is known as Agriculture” (Majid Husain,2008)pp17, Agricultural development in terms of the expansion of agricultural land through major land use changes, increase in agricultural productivity

and net agricultural production. Through the application of modern scientific techniques and advanced technology, increased production; and use of agrochemicals, expansion of irrigation facilities and irrigated area, development of high yielding varieties of seeds in order to meet the food requirement of ever-increasing population of the country these factors helped to solve the food problem of India but it has also created hazardous environmental problems of serious concern. Though the place of agricultural development has to be maintained if we do not want to let the teeming millions die of hunger. Meanwhile, environmental degradation should not be allowed to continue due to agricultural development because it would also cause irreparable loss of human society. (Savindar Singh, 2008, pp 56)

Recently environmental degradation is a burning issue in developing countries. According to Tata Energy Research Institute (1998), environmental degradation covers water, soil, forest and air. Among these, soil Salinization is an important determinant of environmental degradation in India. About 187.8 million hectares (approximately 57%) out of 328.27 million hectares of land areas have been degraded in the country. Among these 10.1 million hectares suffers from soil salinity problem. It occurs mainly due to two factors viz. physical and chemical. The physical factors affect the fertility of the topsoil through wind and water, whereas the chemical factors affect the nutrients of the soil due to deforestation, poor cultivation practices and intensive/repeated irrigation, excess chemical fertilizers, pesticides. According to National Remote Sensing Agency (NRSA), there are eight important types of land degradation. As stated by the NRSA, the eight types of land degradation are Gully land i.e. ravenous, upland with or without scrubs, waterlogged means, dry land and swampy land, salinity and alkalinity land, shifting cultivation areas, degraded

pastures and grazing lands, degraded land under plantation crops, mining and industrial wastelands.

To define the concept of environmental degradation is a poser task. The World Bank's (1992) World Development Report cites deforestation, land degradation, water shortage and contamination, air pollution, and the loss of biodiversity as some of the many environmental problems. We face today in both developed and developing countries. However, unlike poverty which can be defined, at the minimum, based on human nutritional requirements, environmental degradation comprises a large degree of subjectivity on the part of the agents involved or who own the resources. Different societies placed varied ecosystems and different values on environmental resources. Make the definition of environmental degradation difficult and complex. A common solution is to use the physical characteristics of the system as a threshold level beyond which degradation is assumed to take place. There are scarce attempts to know the ecosystem and detailed importance of the ecosystem; were before these physical thresholds can be determined. To minimize conflicts in the analysis, we shall use a combination of ecological thresholds and revealed preferences appropriate as indicators of environmental degradation.

Objective:

- 1) To study the study area's geographical setting and socio-economic setup.
- 2) To study the impact of agricultural development on Water in Walwa Tahsil.
- 3) To suggest appropriate measures for control of water degradation.

Study Area:

The Selected area for the present investigation is the Sangli district of Maharashtra state containing 10 tahsils in Sangli district such as Miraj, Tasgaon, Kavathe-Mahankal, Jat, Khanapur (Vita), Palus, Atpadi, Walwa, Kadegaon, Shirala.

Sangli is one of the southern Districts of Maharashtra lying between 16°43' and 17°38' north latitude and 73°41' and 75°41' east longitude and has an area of 8,572 Sq. Km (2.78% of State) and a population of 28,22,143, (2.51% of State (2011)).

Database and Methodology:

The present study is based on Primary data. Primary data regarding environmental quality, status, etc. will be collected by conducting the intensive fieldwork. The Stratify random sampling technique will be used to select the samples. The sample of Bases of Irrigated 10 Tahsils and non-irrigated 10 Thasil, the 10 tahsils considered based on agricultural development. The secondary data will be counted from related books, published and unpublished reports, journals, newspapers, government reports, District census Handbook, District Statistical Abstract, socio-economic reviews, etc.

Methodology:

The Stratify random sampling technique will be used to select the samples. The sample of Bases of Irrigated Village- from 10 Tahsils-20 Villages Sample selected of the soil and water testing and non-Irrigated Village- 10 Thasil

Composite Index of Development: -

1. Net sown area to Total Geographical area
2. Percentage of Cultivate area to net Sown area
3. Percentage of the net irrigated area to net sown area.

4. The number of tractors available per 100 hectares of cultivated area.
5. The number of electrical pumps available per 100 hectares.
6. Chemical Fertilizer consumption per 100 hectares. Of the net sown area.
7. The number of livestock per 100 hectares. of the net sown area
8. The productivity of 100 hectares. Of the net sown area.
9. Percentage of irrigated wells. Per 100 hectares.
10. Percentage of Literacy to the Total Geographical Area.

The method adopted to determine the levels of development involves two stages. First, the determination of a level of each Revenue circle in terms of discrete variables and second the integration of values obtained to give a complete index of development taking all indices into account. The coefficient of development of each Revenue circle in terms of single variables is expressed as follows:

$$CD_i = \frac{P_i}{PI}$$

Where,

CD_i = the coefficient of development for variable 'i', P_i = percentage of variable 'i', PI = mean percentage of variable 'i' in the whole region

$$CID = \frac{CDi1 + CDi2 + CDi3 + \dots + CDin}{N}$$

Where,

CID = Composite index of development

N = Number of variables.

i= Variable

Levels of Agricultural Development:

1. Higher Level of Development:

The above 10 composite indexes of development have occurred only in walwa, Palus, kadegaon and Miraj tahsil; farming is generally carried out with a commercial and intensive attitude and by adopting new technology. It helps for the development of agriculture. These Tahsils have more irrigated facilities such as river, canal, well, and tube well irrigation; a large area is under availability of irrigation sources and high development is due to the highly fertile soil, climate condition, water supply, and concentration of the agro-based industries in this tahsil.

2. Moderate Level of Development:

These are fall in this category with Shirala, Tasgaon, Jat, and Khanapur composite index of development respectively in Shirala, Tasgaon, Jat and Khanapur has less area in terms of net sown area but rich in underground water and canal irrigation and artificial water supply. In Shirala, Tasgaon the progress of the

development is witnessed and In Jat and Khanapur few areas are irrigated but not for a Narger area covered in irrigation. Few pockets where agricultural development takes place.

3. Lower Levels of Development:

In this category two Thasil have been reported nearly Kavathemhankal and Atpadi; it happened due to rugged topography, fewer irrigation facilities coarse soil, and less use of new form technology and use of fertilizers in these tahsils. Also, have poorer irrigation facilities thereby the requirements of other inputs in agricultural practices were less in factors within this tahsil may attain faster development when water is made available by ongoing irrigation projects in this tahsil so the development growth rate is increasing in this study region.

A calculated composite index of ten tahsils out of which Shirala, Tasgaon, Khanapur, Jat, Atpadi, and Kavathemhankal tahsil has shown progress in agriculture when few effective factors play a major role in the development such as deep, black soil, intensive cultivation and assent water supply and sugar, dairy farming and other small-scale and larger-scale factories. Kavathemhankal, Jat, Atpadi, and Khana agricultural development growth due to using agricultural implements are poor in this in this tahsil of the study region.

Composite Index of Development and levels of Development

Sr. No.	2020-21			2023-24		
	Tahsil	CID	Level of Development	Tahsil	CID	Level of Development
1	Walwa	14.44	Higher Level of Development	Walwa	16.94	Higher Level of Development
2	Miraj	11.05	Higher Level of Development	Palus	12.99	Higher Level of Development
3	Tasgaon	9.88	Moderately High Level of Development	Kadegaon	11.97	Higher Level of Development
4	Khanapur	8.74	Moderately High Level of Development	Miraj	10.03	Higher Level of Development
5	Shirala	8.17	Moderately High Level of Development	Jat	9.34	Moderately High Level of Development
6	Jat	8.18	Moderately High Level of Development	Shirala	9.24	Moderately High Level of Development
7	Kavathe Mahankal	7.43	Lower Level of Development	Tasgaon	8.67	Moderately High Level of Development
8	Atpadi	7.25	Lower Level of Development	Khanapur	8.77	Moderately High Level of Development
9	Kadegaon	-	-	Kavathe Mahankal	6.21	Lower Level of Development
10	Palus	-	-	Atpadi	6.33	Lower Level of Development

(Source: - Calculate by Researcher) Below 8 low lower Level, Above 8 Moderately High, Above 10 Higher Level

Levels of Agricultural Development (2020-21 to 2023-24)

CLUSTER ANALYSIS OF THE YEAR 2020-21 and 2023-24

Ten tahsils of the study area are Grouped into ten clusters for the hierarchical

cluster analysis of 2001-01, and ascending order of hierarchy is preferred.

Causes of Water Degradation in Sangli District:

Water pollution caused by fertilizers and pesticides used in agriculture often dispersed over large areas is a great threat to fresh groundwater ecosystems. The highest nitrate concentration in groundwater is the leaching of the residual nitrate due to the excessive as well as intensive use of chemical fertilizers in farms and fields. Even indiscriminate disposal of human and animal waste on land is another reason of it. In India, agriculture area is more, the fertilizers and pesticides are continuously used get mixed into water and pollute the surface water and groundwater. The part of this percolates into the ground and pollutes the

groundwater directly. Nitrate concentration is above the permissible level of Ph in 11 states in India. DDT, BHC, Carbonate, Endosulfan, etc. are the most common pesticides used in India. But, the vulnerability of groundwater to pesticide and fertilizer pollution is governed by soil texture, the pattern of fertilizer and pesticide use, their degradation products, and total organic matter in the soil. Use of Fertilizers, Use of Pesticides, Cropping Pattern, Improper Crop Rotation, Water Use, Water Logging, Irrigation, Growth of Agricultural Industries, Manure spreading, Tillage/plugging

Changes in Groundwater Quality from 2000-01 Irrigated Villages

Water Parameter(10500:1991) (Bureau of Indian standard)																					
Sr. No.	Tahsil	Sample Village	No. of Sample(Well/ Tube well)	pH (7-8.5)	EC(<1)	TDS (500mg/lit)	Hardness (200mg/l)	Chloride(200mg/lit)	BOD (30mg/lit)	DO (4mg/lit)	NO3-N (45mg/lit)	COD (250mg/lit)	Sulphets (200 mg/lit)	Copper (0.05 ppm)	Ferous (1-0.05mg/lit)	Zinc (5 ppm)	Cadmium (0.01 ppm)	mercury (0.01ppm)	lead (0.1 ppm)	Alkalinity (200 mg/lit)	iron (0.3 to 1.0 mg/lit)
2	WALAWA	Junekhed(W)	1	7.5	1	469	179	155	27	3.9	39	211	127	0.01	0.07	2.8	0.01	0.01	0.01	176	0.1
		Borgaon(B)	1	7.6	0.8	459	189	170	28	3.8	39	221	156	0.02	0.08	2.9	0.01	0.01	0.02	150	0.9

(Source:- Water testing Department Sangli)

Changes in Groundwater Quality from 2010-11 Irrigated Villages

Water Parameter(10500:1991) (Bureau of Indian standard)																					
Sr.No.	Tahsil	Sample Village	No. of Sample(Well/ Tube well)	pH (7-8.5)	EC(<1)	TDS (500mg/lit)	Hardness (200mg/l)	Chloride(200mg/lit)	BOD (30mg/lit)	DO (4mg/lit)	NO3-N (45mg/lit)	COD (250mg/lit)	Sulphets (200 mg/lit)	Copper (0.05 ppm)	Ferous (1-0.05mg/lit)	Zinc (5 ppm)	Cadmium (0.01 ppm)	mercury (0.01ppm)	lead (0.1 ppm)	Alkalinity (200 mg/lit)	iron (0.3 to 1.0 mg/lit)
2	WALAWA	Junekhed(W)	1	8.20	1.1	496	179	195	20	2.2	41	233	189	0.02	1.04	3.3	0.0	0.01	0.05	194	0.08
		Borgaon(B)	1	8.10	1	489	189	190	21	3.1	40	228	195	0.02	1.05	4.0	0.0	0.01	0.10	190	0.09

(Source:- Water testing Department Sangli)

Changes in Groundwater Quality from 2023-24 Irrigated Villages

Water Parameter(10500:1991) (Bureau of Indian standard)																					
Sr. No.	Tahsil	Sample Village	No. of Sample (Well / Tube well)	pH (7-8.5)	EC(<1)	TDS (500mg/lit)	Hardness (200mg/l)	Chloride(200mg/lit)	BOD (30mg/lit)	DO (4mg/lit)	NO3-N (45mg/lit)	COD (250mg/lit)	Sulphates (200 mg/lit)	Copper (0.05 ppm)	Ferrous (1-0.05mg/lit)	Zinc (5 ppm)	Cadmium (0.01 ppm)	mercury (0.01 ppm)	lead (0.1 ppm)	Alkalinity (200 mg/lit)	iron (0.3 to 1.0 mg/lit)
2	WALAWA	Junekhed(W)	1	8.7	1.6	503	207	186	16	1.9	43	250	193	0.03	1.50	5.1	0.04	0.03	0.40	210	1.1
		Borgaon(B)	1	8.5	1.6	501	203	179	22	2.7	42	252	197	0.05	1.70	5.2	0.02	0.04	0.20	213	1

(Source:-Field Visit)

Groundwater Quality Irrigated Villages

Conclusion:

The study of the levels of agricultural development reveals that the Most Backward, Backward, Developing, Developed, and More Developed level of agricultural development is confined to areas with assured water supply. The dominance of Wheat, Jawar, and sugarcane farming, social awareness among the farmers, the Cooperative movement, and the role of sugar industries have played a significant role in the development of the agricultural level

After analyzing the underground water, it is yet to be seen that, in the village of Irrigated Villages Tahsil, during the period from 2001 to 2023-24 the result of agricultural development has shown that during the period the average quantity pH is respectively as 8.06 in 7. 21 pH 7. 55 pH 8. 06 This means that pH - has increased 7.5 respectively within the same period, TDS is (367.1, 411. 25, 454) Hardness is (157, 168. 60, 186.9) and growing respectively. The

change in all the above 18 parameters means that the changes in the quantity of underground water are due to the additional factors used in agriculture. Electrical conductivity (<0.77, <0.99, <1.62), chlorides respectively (15 9, 181.55, 166) .4) has decreased the number of accounts of BOD is (24.45, 20.05, 17.7) decreased, respectively (3.3, 2.85, 2.11) because of the use of extra fertilizer. NO3 respectively (32.95, 40.00, 42) whereas the alkalinity also has been changed ratio is (151.6, 174.05, 184.55) respectively, in the irrigated tahsil, changes are found in underground water samples of the village.

All these changes are found in the selected villages from the irrigated tahsil, and the effects on water changed the ecological elements of agriculture, which are affected by malpractices in the agriculture sector. with these in 18 parameters appear to be changed in the water flow is changed, due to the irrigation scheme. This water was used for farming in diffusion but now the

adverse effect of this development seen on the farm is now visible from above analysis. Therefore, farming has grown due to the modernization of the farming but it had a negative impact on the environmental development is seen today; Water, walwa tahsil there is need to forget that care of these factors. And it is understood from the fact that agriculture is affecting variable like soil, water and vegetation life sources on earth. Water is one of the most essential natural resources, to sustain life on earth planet, but the scarcity of it is a worldwide issue within last few decades and still, it is experienced critically now also. Its demands, rapid increase in population and expanding the economy of the country. Variations in climatic characteristics both in space and time are responsible for uneven distribution of precipitation in India. It is posing a challenge to the existing water resources and those who are responsible for the management of water resources. Hydrological studies are required to be taken up for assessment of water resources under

changing climatic scenarios. For safe drinking water, it is essential to generate reliable and accurate information about water quality. To sustain life on earth in all its totality, water should be carefully managed in its natural habitats.

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